

Determinant of Employee Turnover Intention in Government Organization: Study in Aceh Women Empowerment and Children Protection Board

^{1*}Nana Nosra, ¹Hafasnuddin, ¹T. Meldi Kesuma

¹Department of Management, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia

Abstract: This study is to determine the effect of talent management and global mindset on organization commitment and its impact on turnover intention. The object is the Aceh Women Empowerment and Children Protection Board (BP3A), as a Government organization in province level, which is located inorganizational commitmentg technique used in this study is the "census" method so that the sample is as much as 146 respondents. To test and analyze the data, the Patial Least Square (PLS) is used. The result shows that: talent management has a significant effect on organization commitment; talent management has a significant and negative effect on turnover intention; global mindset has a significant and positive effect on the organization commitment; global mindset has a significant and negative effect on turnover intention, and; organization commitment does not have a significant effect on the turnover intention. Especially for the talent management that has a significant effect on turnover intention, and also for the global mindset that has a significant effect on turnover intention, these both have a negative effect. This verification research integrates the causalities among variable based on the previous theories, and verify it to be new premise. This is verified by PLS technique with research model developed, new time and new object. The limitation lies in the number of variables and object. The result contributes to science development and this can update the causality theories to be a base for further researcher to develop new models. This is also as a reference for the practical managers to pay more attention related to the variables, to develop the right policies in their organization.

Keywords : Talent Management, Global Mindset, Organization Commitment, Turnover Intention

I. Introduction

Turnover intention is one of the hot issues discussed especially in government institutions, because this issue has a political nuance, meaning that there is often a pull between the leaders of an agency with other institutions so that many employees are transferred when there is a change of leadership in the institution itself. Employee turnover is a work stability index. Excessive turnover is of course undesirable and costs a lot (Gaol, 2014).

The Aceh Women Empowerment and Children Protection Board (BP3A) is a government organization that operates in empowering women and protecting the children. This organization is located in Aceh at the province level. Based on the author's observation, there are currently several problems that occur in this organization such as the placement of employees which is not in accordance with their expertise so that employees work no longer in accordance with their expectations, giving rise to the desire of employees to move to other places in their fields. . This condition is known as turnover intention. (Rokhmah & Riani, 2005) state turnover intention is usually one of the last choices for an employee if he finds that his working conditions are no longer in line with what he expected. Alniaçik, Alniaçik, Erat, & Akçin (2013) describe turnover intention is defined as the desire of employees to move or stop from the organization they work for. According to Lum et al in Prihati, Oetomo, & Utomo (2012), the turnover intention component, namely the need to find new jobs in the same field with different agencies. Supriyanto (2003) figures that turnover is as the proportion of the number of organizational members that are voluntary and not (non-voluntary) leaving the organization within a certain period of time. According to (Lum, Kervin, Clark, Reid, & Sirola, 1998), Mathis and Jackson (2006) in (Putra, 2019) state that turnover intention is the most relevant variable and more likely to explain turnover behavior.

There are several studies regarding the relationship between organization commitment and turnover intention. Alniaçik et al., 2013 states that employees with high affective commitment will be more motivated to a higher level of current

performance, and this will reduce the intention of employees to move to work elsewhere. Organization commitment reflects how an individual identifies himself with an organization and is bound by its purpose. Employees who have satisfaction with their jobs, salaries given, coworkers, promotion opportunities, and supervision provided by the organization will be committed to the organization. Every employee has special skills to complete the tasks that have been charged to him. Therefore, each agency should choose employees who are competent to fill responsibilities in certain positions because it involves achieving established organizational goals Moehariono (2012). The concept of employee commitment to the organization (also called work commitment), which gets the attention of managers and organizational behavior experts, develops from the initial study of employee loyalty that is expected to exist on each employee. Work commitment or organizational commitment is a condition that is felt by employees that can lead to strong positive behavior towards the work organization they have. According to Steers; & Porter (1991), a form of work commitment that arises is not only passive loyalty, but also involves active relationships with work organizations that have the goal of providing all efforts for the success of the work organization concerned. (Qadariah, Majid, & Idris, 2019) say that employee commitment to the organization is very important factor for organizations in positioning the employees to hold positing and in promoting the staff for higher official strategic positions. (Luthans, 2006) in (Majid, Basri, Nopita, & Fahlevi, 2016) figures that organizational commitment is an attitude displaying the "loyalty" of an employee and it is a continuing process through which a member of an organization expresses his attention to the success of the organization.

(Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 1982) define work commitment as the relative strength of individual identification and its involvement with work organizations. While (Michael & Weintin, 1993) view work commitment as a value orientation towards work that shows that individuals think deeply about their work, work gives life satisfaction, and jobs give status to individuals. Commitment to the organization is the desire of employees to remain a part of an organization based on three dimensions, namely: affective commitment, continuance commitment, normative commitment. Organizations must give full attention and make employees believe in the organization, so that employees will get commitment. If employee commitment has been obtained, employees will be loyal and able to work as well as possible for the benefit of the organization. This situation is very good for achieving organizational goals, because the organization gets full support from its members so that it can concentrate fully on priority goals so that it will improve performance.

Research conducted by (Rana & Abbasi, 2013) says that talent management has a direct impact on the turnover rate carried out by employees, therefore leaders generally need special skills to be more aware and vigilant in developing the careers of employees, so that employees able to increase productivity. In an organization, it is desirable to be more advanced than employees, so that it will be easier to enter the global market. With the high turnover rate on employees will create concern from the image of the organization

In the reality that is currently happening at the BP3A this talent management has not been able to be applied maximally. So that many conditions found in the field are not as expected. For example, the low ability of employees due to work in their field is not in accordance with the knowledge they have, of course this is related to talent management that does not place the position of employees in accordance with their fields. Even though the talent management system is applied to create competent and competent human resources and be able to occupy key positions in each agency.

(Aksakal, Dağdeviren, Eraslan, & Yüksel, 2013) explain that talent management is a process carried out to place employees in the right position in their jobs. Talent management also provides opportunities for employees to conduct training and improve their abilities. According to (Fischer, Sergevnin, & Zadorskaya, 2001) talent management is a systematic activity that contributes to the development of potential talents. Talent management is expected to increase competitive advantage, organizational performance and be able to maximize organizational productivity. In talent management analysis carried out includes three processes, namely Input, Process, and Output. (Armstrong, 2006) defines talent management as the process of identifying, developing, recruiting, retaining, and disseminating talented people. Whereas according to (Cheese, Craig, & Thomas, 2007) in (Febriani, 2012) talent management is a process carried out by the company to fulfill and anticipate the company's needs for Human Resources.

Thus talent management is closely related to the selection process to the development process carried out on employees. To be able to produce high-quality organizations must go through very long processes that focus on high-performing employees. In the process of developing and improving employee competencies, a process that is able to create changes in employees is needed. One way that is used to develop employees is the mindset of agency management. In providing the best service, agencies must be forced to be able to expand the network. Thus each agency is able to adapt by training and developing managers with a global mindset.

The phenomenon that also often occurs in every current Aceh government agency is like often employees are transferred from one agency to another then transferred again to the previous agency, because of the low performance

and not in line with the employee's expectations (Survey Results 2018). These conditions have an impact on the level of commitment and employee turnover rates. There are employees who feel uncomfortable with their superiors; this can also indicate that the employees are not comfortable working in the agency. In the past one year many employees decided to leave the agency due to several reasons. The employee's desire to leave causes greatly disrupts the concentration of employees in carrying out their work.

Another factor that also affects commitment and turnover is the global mindset. Arora (2004) generally states that global mindset (global mindset) is a type of attribute that will improve function and performance in the global environment. This can be equated attributes such as point of view, behavior and philosophy. In general, with the global mindset of managers, it is expected that they will be able to increase employee morale and be able to build a commitment between employees. Today's commitment from employees to the organization has received much attention supported by an attitude of attachment and a sense of responsibility towards the organization because it is seen as something they should do according to their responsibilities as employees. With quality standards set by agencies, employees are also required to be more competent and able to improve quality.

Based on research conducted by (Raman, Chadee, Roxas, & Michailova, 2013) the organization is a reflection of how managers manage the company so that employees are able to improve their performance. Thus, it is expected that employees will have an attachment to the company and will be more committed to the company. To achieve a corporate goal can not be separated from the role of employees and managers who work in order to be able to achieve the company goals that have been set. Based on research conducted by (Vural, Vardarlier, & Aykir, 2012) the mission and responsibility of the organization is to create a policy strategy to develop the vision. While talent management is not only to maximize organizational performance, but also talent management has a positive influence on organizational commitment. Thus there is a kind of interest in talent management to increase organizational commitment.

Global mindset according to (Arora, Jaju, Kefalas, & Perenich, 2004) is a point of view that will improve function and performance in the global environment. According to (Javidan & Bowen, 2013) global mindset is the ability of individuals to influence other individuals. The global mindset is basically a psychological process that suggests that there are ways to get the changes that are expected, by changing people's mindsets, because those people will bring about the changes themselves. According to (Felício, Caldeirinha, & Ribeiro-Navarrete, 2015) a corporate mindset is a combination of thoughts from individuals with individual interactions in an organization, which will increase commitment between employees and the company.

(Gupta & Govindarajan, 2002) divide the global mindset into two orientations. Precisely the global mindset describes a combination of open attitudes and awareness of various cultural differences and values. Global mindset is also as a set of mental images and assumptions used by individuals to continue learning from experience. Global mindset can be used at the organizational and individual levels. The previous meaning was reaffirmed by (Beamish, Killing, Lecraw, & Morrison, 1994) with the characteristics of people who have a global mindset, namely the ability to develop and use global strategy skills, the ability to manage change and transition, the ability to work together in teams and others.

Based on the problem identification above, the model and hypothesis that can be provided as follows:

Figure1. Research Paradigm

- H1: Talent management influences organization commitment significantly
- H2: Talent management influences turnover intention significantly
- H3: Global mindest influences organization commitment significantly
- H4: Global mindset influences turnover intention significantly
- H5: Organizational commitment influences turnover intention significantly

II. Method

The object in this research is the BP3A as a government organization and the population is all its employees, which is currently as much as 146 people. The sampling technique used is the census so that the sample is as much as the population, it is 146 respondents. This is a verification research that tests the causality of the variables that is expected to able to answer the hypothesis. The questionnaire uses liker scale to measure indicators. To test the hypothesis and analyze the data, the Partial Least Square (PLS) method is used, with smartPLS software. PLS is not concerned with a strong theory and does not require data to have a normal distribution (Latan & Ghazali, 2012). From the same source (Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009), (Pirouz, 2012), and (Tenenhaus, 2008) revealed that one of the advantages of PLS is that it can handle complex models with multiple exogenous and endogenous variables with many indicators, which can be used on small sample sizes and can overcome variables with nominal, ordinal, and continues types.

In this research, the constructs build from several previous researches as references, that are : 1) (Harnoto, 2002) states that turnover intentions are characterized by various matters concerning employee behavior, including: increased absenteeism, lazy work, increased courage to violate work rules, courage to oppose or protest to superiors, or Positive behavior that is very different from usual; 2) (Steers; & Porter, 1991) describe that organizational commitment is measured using indicators, namely : there is a high level of trust in the workplace institution; the existence of pride for the workplace institution as a good institution for work; the desire to preserve and maintain the good name of the institution where it works; opportunities for making decisions to improve institutional performance, and; uphold the principle of freedom by not reducing concern for the future of the institution where it works. ;3) (Aksakal et al., 2013) figures that talent management can be seen from several indicators, namely: evaluate the performance of talented employees; recruit talented people; select talented people; develop talented people; retain talented people; distribute talented people appropriately according to their talents, and; ensuring organizational performance can be maintained by investing in human resources.; 4) (Arora et al., 2004) says global mindset can be seen from several indicators : happy to look at the global environment; trying to make conclusions from various phenomena that occur; can trigger the spirit to succeed in doing something that is creative; have standard criteria for performance and achievement of goals; ensuring achievement through the right process; trying to ensure participation and contribute when making decisions; trying to ensure creativity and innovation become the center of the learning process

III. Result

Figure 2. Outer Loading Model

In the figure 2 indicates that from the outer model there is not one indicator of the analyzed variable that can be excluded. It shows the value of the outer model or the correlation between constructs and the analyzed variables already meet convergent validity because all indicators have a loading factor value above 0.50. So it can be concluded that all constructs on each variable tested with the modification model have fulfilled convergent validity.

Table 1. Path Coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values)

Variable	Sample (O)	Average of Sample (M)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Global Mindset -> Organization Commitment	0.287	0.294	4.398	0.000
Global Mindset -> Turnover Intention	0.249	0.240	4.090	0.000
Organization Commitment -> Turnover Intention	0.157	0.172	1.868	0.064
Talent Management -> Organization Commitment	0.684	0.679	11.073	0.000
Talent Management -> Turnover Intention	0.586	0.580	7.848	0.000

From the table 1 above it explains as follows.

H1 : Accepted

The result shows that there is a significant influence of talent management on organization commitment. If there is an increase of 1 towards talent management, the level of organizational commitment will increase 0.684 unit. The result is in line with (Vural et al., 2012) that says talent management has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This condition is also considered in accordance with the reality that occurred in the field that the staffs of the BP3A have a very good level of talent management so that this condition has a positive impact on improving and strengthening organizational commitment. Strengthening talent management can be conducted by recruiting and placing employees in accordance with their talents so that they can ensure that they form a good commitment to the organization they work in.

H2 : Accepted

Talent management has a significant but negative effect on the turnover intention. If there is an increase of 1 unit in talent management, the level of turnover intention will decrease 0.694 unit. This result is in line with the research conducted by (Rana & Abbasi, 2013) that talent management has a direct impact on the level of turnover intention carried out by employees, therefore leaders generally need special skills to be more aware and vigilant in developing careers employees and place employees according to expertise so that employees are able to increase their productivity. In an organization, a leader is desirable to be more advanced than employees, so that it will be easier to enter global conditions. With the high turnover rate on employees will create concern from the image of the organization. Based on the results of field assessments, it was found that the implementation of excellent talent management has an impact on reducing turnover intention. Talent employees need to be maintained so that the intention turnover level can be suppressed.

H3 : Accepted

The result indicates that there is a significant effect of global mindset on the turnover intention. The path coefficient of 0.287 means that if there is an increase in 1 unit global mindset, it directly and significantly influences the organizational commitment as much as 0.287 unit. This result is also in line with the research conducted by (Raman et al., 2013) that the global mindset has a positive influence on organizational commitment. The description found in the field also confirms this statement. The staff of the BP3A agrees on average if employees who have a good level of global mindset will influence the level of organizational commitment in a good direction. Employees who have a good global mindset level try to ensure their participation and contribution when making decisions for the organization, which means they have high commitment in the organization.

H4 : Accepted

The global mindset with path coefficient 0.294 has a significant but negative effect on the turnover intention. If there is an increase of 1 unit in the global mindset, the turnover intention will decrease 0.294 unit. This result is in line with the research conducted by (Raman et al., 2013) that concludes with the high level of awareness of foreign cultures and the economy generally, the competition in the market will continue. With the existence of a global mindset that is owned by top managers and employees, it is expected that more knowledge will be opened to top managers and employees in working and interacting in organizations, so that it will have an impact on reducing the turnover intention level. The authors' observations in the field also show the global mindset influences turnover intention significantly. Employees who have a good global mindset tend to be more creative and can trigger their enthusiasm to succeed in doing something to achieve their organizational goals, so they can reduce turnover intention in themselves.

H5 : Rejected

Organizational commitment does not have a significant effect and with negative effect on the turnover intention. The result of this hypothesis are not in line with (Alniaçik et al., 2013) who argues that employees with high affective commitment will be more motivated to a higher level of current performance, and this will reduce intention employee to transfer work elsewhere. However, the result of statistical test is in line with the reality in the field, namely the level of turnover intention of the staff of the BP3A does not depend on the level of organizational commitment. Even though the level of organizational commitment is good, they can move from one government agency to another in a broad scope to pursue their career to a better level.

IV. Conclusion

The result shows that: talent management has a significant effect on organization commitment; talent management has a significant effect on turnover intention; global mindset has a significant effect on the organization commitment;

global mindset has a significant effect on turnover intention, and; organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on the turnover intention. Especially for the talent management that has a significant effect on turnover intention, it has a negative effect which means that when talent management increases, it would decrease the turnover intention in the organization. Also for the global mindset that has a significant effect on turnover intention; it has a negative effect that means when the global mind set increase it will decrease the turnover intention in the organization.

This verification research integrates the causalities amongs variables based on the previous theories, and verify it to be new premise. This is verified by PLS technique as a new from the previous ones, with research model developed, with a new time and a new object. The limitation lies in the number of variables and object. The result contributes to science development and this can update the causality theories to be a base for further researcher to develop new models. This is also as a reference for the practical managers to pay more attention related to the variables, to develop the right policies in their organization.

Reference

- [1.] Aksakal, E., Dağdeviren, M., Eraslan, E., & Yüksel, İ. (2013). Personel Selection based on Talent Management. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 73, 68-72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.02.021>
- [2.] Alniaçik, E., Alniaçik, Ü., Erat, S., & Akçin, K. (2013). Does person-organization fit moderate the effects of affective commitment and job satisfaction on turnover intentions? *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 99, 274-281. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.495>
- [3.] Armstrong, M. (2006). *Strategic Human Resource Management-A Guide to Action 3rd Ed* (3rd Editio). Retrieved from [http://repository.umpwr.ac.id:8080/bitstream/handle/123456789/521/Strategic Human Resource Management -A Guide to Action 3rd Ed.pdf?sequence=1](http://repository.umpwr.ac.id:8080/bitstream/handle/123456789/521/Strategic%20Human%20Resource%20Management%20-A%20Guide%20to%20Action%203rd%20Ed.pdf?sequence=1)
- [4.] Arora, A., Jaju, A., Kefalas, A. G., & Perenich, T. (2004). An exploratory analysis of global managerial mindsets: a case of US textile and apparel industry. *Journal of International Management*, 10(3), 393-411. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intman.2004.05.001>
- [5.] Beamish, P. W., Killing, J. P., Lecraw, D. J., & Morrison, A. J. (1994). *International Management* (Burr Ridge, IL: Irwin).
- [6.] Cheese, P., Craig, E., & Thomas, R. J. (2007). *The talent powered organization: Strategies for globalization, talent management and high performance*. Retrieved from https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=kRvHo65IUSMC&oi=fnd&pg=PP2&dq=The+Talent+Powered+Organization,+Strategies+for+Globalization,+Talent+Management,+and+High+Performance&ots=K7FVYNWePb&sig=Owv9fAKAO2235Fj2en3o-M-ymIE&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=The T
- [7.] Febriani, A. D. (2012). Pengaruh Talent Management Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Pusat Bank X. Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Indonesia.
- [8.] Felício, J. A., Caldeirinha, V. R., & Ribeiro-Navarrete, B. (2015). Corporate and individual global mind-set and internationalization of European SMEs. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(4), 797-802. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.11.031>
- [9.] Fischer, R. J., Sergevnin, V. A., & Zadorskaya, D. A. (2001). A New Paradigm for Police Officer Retention: Intellectual Capital v. the Law Enforcement Officer. *Illinois Law Enforcement Executive Forum*, 1(3), 21. Retrieved from [https://iletsbeiforumjournal.com/images/Issues/FreeIssues/ILEEF 2001-1.3.pdf](https://iletsbeiforumjournal.com/images/Issues/FreeIssues/ILEEF%202001-1.3.pdf)
- [10.] Gaol, C. H. R. J. L. (2014). *A to Z human capital* (Ninuk, Ed.). Jakarta: Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.
- [11.] Gupta, A. K., & Govindarajan, V. (2002). Cultivating a global mindset. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 16(1), 116-126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5465/ame.2002.6640211>
- [12.] Harnoto. (2002). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* (Edisi Kedu). Jakarta: PT. Prehallindo.

- [13.] Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. *Advances in International Marketing*, 20(May 2014), 277-319. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979\(2009\)0000020014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014)
- [14.] Javidan, M., & Bowen, D. (2013). The 'global mindset' of managers. *Organizational Dynamics*, 42(2), 145-155. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2013.03.008>
- [15.] Latan, H., & Ghozali, I. (2012). *Partial Least Square: Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi SmartPLS 2.0 M3*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [16.] Lum, L., Kervin, J., Clark, K., Reid, F., & Sirola, W. (1998). Explaining nursing turnover intent: job satisfaction, pay satisfaction, or organizational commitment? *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 19(3), 305-320.
- [17.] Luthans, F. (2006). *Perilaku Organisasi (Edisi 10)*. (v. A. Yuwono, S. Purwanti, TA P, & W. Rosari, Trans.) Yogyakarta: ANDI.
- [18.] Majid, M. S. A., Basri, H., Nopita, E., & Fahlevi, H. (2016). The Effect of Organizational Culture , Leadership Style , and Functional Position on Organizational Commitment and Their Impact on The Performance of Internal Auditors in Aceh , Indonesia. *BRAND. Broad Research in Accounting, Negotiation, and Distribution*, 7(1), 37-50. <https://doi.org/2067-8177>
- [19.] Michael, L., & Weintin, H. P. (1993). Money is everything. *Annual Report HR*, 3.
- [20.] Moehersono. (2012). *Pengukuran Kinerja Berbasis Kompetensi (Revision)*. Rajawali Pers, Ekonomi/Manajemen.
- [21.] Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., & Steers, R. (1982). *Organizational linkages: The psychology of commitment, absenteeism, and turnover*. San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- [22.] Pirouz, D. M. (2012). An Overview of Partial Least Squares. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (October 2006). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1631359>
- [23.] Prihati, M. A., Oetomo, H. W., & Utomo, S. B. (2012). Compensation analysis to intention to quit by using organization commitment as the intervening variable. *EKUITAS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)*, 16(1), 1-15. Retrieved from <http://perpustakaan.unitomo.ac.id/repository/20140717001.pdf>
- [24.] Putra, T. R. I. (2019). T. Roli Ilhamsyah Putra Department of Management, Syiah Kuala University, 23111, Indonesia. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 2(01), 124-132. Retrieved from <https://ijbmer.org/view1.php?issue=1>
- [25.] Qadariah, Majid, M. S. A., & Idris, S. (2019). Mediating Effect of Employee Performance on the Influences of Job Embeddedness , Self-efficacy , and Organizational Commitment on the Public Organizational Performance. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 21(2), 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2102015562>
- [26.] Raman, R., Chadee, D., Roxas, B., & Michailova, S. (2013). Effects of partnership quality, talent management, and global mindset on performance of offshore IT service providers in India. *Journal of International Management*, 19(4), 333-346. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intman.2013.03.010>
- [27.] Rana, A. H., & Abbasi, A. S. (2013). Impact Of Talent Management And Employee Turnover Intention On Organizational Efficiency-A Case Of Telecommunication Sector Of Pakistan. *Science International*, 25(3), 637-642. Retrieved from <http://www.sci-int.com/pdf/202512997537-637-642-Aiza-TM & OE-Sci Int-GP-Final.pdf>
- [28.] Rokhmah, B. E., & Riani, A. L. (2005). Keterkaitan antara komitmen afektif dengan intensi turnover pada karyawan bagian produksi di PT. Usman Jaya Mekar Magelang. *Jurnal Ilmiah Teknik Industri*, 4(2), 78-85. <https://doi.org/10.23917/jiti.v4i2.1366>

- [29.] Steers, R. M., & Porter, L. W. (1991). *Motivation and work behavior* (Fifth edit). New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin Boston, MA.
- [30.] Supriyanto. (2003). *Metodologi Riset, Surabaya: Administrasi & Kebijakan Kesehatan*. Fakultas Kesehatan Masyarakat Universitas Airlangga.
- [31.] Tenenhaus, M. (2008). Component-based structural equation modelling. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 19(7-8), 871-886. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360802159543>
- [32.] Vural, Y., Vardarlier, P., & Aykir, A. (2012). The effects of using talent management with performance evaluation system over employee commitment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 340-349. Retrieved from <https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com>